

August 31, 2024

<https://ijoabs.com/>
[DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.)

Elucidation of *Ralstonia solanacearum* Phylotypes causing Bacterial Wilt in *Solanum lycopersicum* (Cobra tomatoes) through Modified Agar Medium (MAM) and Multiplex-PCR

Author's Details:

Forkwa Etienne Yong^{1**}, Egbe Enow Andrew^{12†}, Eneke Esoeyang Tambe Bechem^{1†}

¹Department of Plant Science, University of Buea Cameroon, P.O.Box 63 Buea 237, Cameroon.

²Faculty of Agriculture and Veterinary Medicine, University of Buea.

*Corresponding author email: forkwayong@gmail.com, phone: +237679155410 †contributing authors:

Forkwa E. Yong carried out the experiment and wrote the first draft manuscript. Egbe E. A. designed the experiment, supervised the work, and corrected the draft manuscript. Eneke E. Tambe Bechem supervised the work, did the data analysis, and corrected the manuscript. All the authors read through the final manuscript.

Received Date: 27-June-2024

Accepted Date: 04-Aug-2024

Published Date: 31-Aug-2024

Abstract

Tomatoes are major staples in global diets and are frequently threatened by the virulent soil-borne pathogen, *Ralstonia solanacearum*, which causes devastating bacterial wilt and poses a significant risk to food security. This study was designed to elucidate the *Ralstonia solanacearum* phylotypes associated with bacterial wilt in *Solanum lycopersicum* in Buea, Cameroon. One hundred and fifty symptomatic tomato plants were collected from five tomatoes producing sites in Buea (Bwitingi, Ewonda, Great Soppo, Molyko, and Muea). A modified agar medium (MAM) was used to minimize the presence of contaminating pathogens, followed by nutrient agar to further purify the 45 isolates. Subsequently, the isolates underwent biochemical tests (Kligler iron agar and Gram staining), pathogenicity tests, genomic DNA extraction, and Polymerase Chain Reaction (Multiplex PCR) using primers that targeted 16S and 23S rRNA. The symptoms observed included wilted and yellow leaves, discoloured stems, and adventitious roots. Spearman correlations showed the strongest associations between discoloured xylem and wilted leaves ($r = 0.43$) and the weakest between discoloured xylem and yellow leaves ($r = 0.13$). Kligler iron agar, Gram stain, and pathogenicity tests confirmed the presence of the pathogen, but no significant differences were found amongst the 45 isolates ($P = 0.05$), except for stem streaming ($H = 11.82$, $P = 0.019$). Genomic DNA was successfully extracted from all 45 isolates, and effectively amplified during PCR, yielding distinct bands of 372, 144, 213, and 91 base pairs, indicating the presence of phylotypes II, I, IV, and III, respectively, in the isolates. These findings provide valuable insights into the pathogen's diversity and identity in Cameroon, providing clues to stakeholders in the management of bacterial wilt disease in the tomato sector

Keywords: *Ralstonia solanacearum*, phylotypes, Modified agar medium, nutrient agar, Primers, PCR, and Gel electrophoresis

INTRODUCTION

Tomatoes (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) are prominent fruits globally (Shibzukhov *et al.*, 2021), and they are renowned for their culinary (Tripodi *et al.*, 2023) and nutritional value (Martinez *et al.*, 2022). With their vivid pigmentation, tomatoes are a treasure trove of beneficial compounds such as lycopene (Petropoulos *et al.*,

August 31, 2024

2020), antioxidants (Włodarczyk *et al.*, 2023) and essential vitamins (Isidro-Requejo *et al.*, 2023). It is an essential ingredient in many culinary practices, as it supports a balanced diet and promote human health (Mayele & Abu, 2023). The high prevalence of *Ralstonia* (a genus of Gram-negative bacteria, encompassing both plant and human pathogens) has been attributed to many factors such as inadequate soil drainage (Gupta *et al.*, 2018), poor irrigation management (Ayankojo *et al.*, 2020), suboptimal nutrient balance (Yusuf *et al.*, 2023), and susceptible cultivars (Umesha & Avinash, 2015). Amongst the *Ralstonia spp.*, *Ralstonia solanacearum* is a highly virulent soil-borne pathogen which causes bacterial wilt disease in various plant species including *Solanum lycopersicum*, posing a significant risk to global food security (Osipitan *et al.*, 2018). The economic impact of bacterial wilt on the tomato industry is substantial, with an estimated annual losses of \$1.67 billion in the United States alone, as reported by Paudel *et al.* (2020).

According to Afanga *et al.* (2022), *Solanum lycopersicum* (Cobra tomatoes) is cultivated by 87.7 % of the tomato farmers in Buea and its environs for its disease resistance and high economic value but recently, bacterial wilt had adversely affected its yield and productivity. Also, Toukam *et al.* (2009) did not include many regions including the Southwest Region (highly affected) during their project of *R. solanacearum* strains isolation in Cameroon. Rapid urbanisation has resulted in reduced farmland and pathogen built-up in farmlands in Buea (Yursiadi, 2020). The bacterium's morphology includes a rod shape with a polar flagellum for motility, while its brown pigment production can be exploited for its diagnosis in culture media (Tessema *et al.*, 2020). *Ralstonia solanacearum* colonises plant roots, forms biofilms, and spreads via the vascular system, leading to plant wilting and death (Mamphogoro, 2020; Planas-Marquès *et al.*, 2020). Genetic diversity within *R. solanacearum* contributes to its ability to infect diverse plant hosts and adapt to varying environmental conditions (Lee and Park, 2016). Other plant pathogenic strains within *Ralstonia* include *Ralstonia syzygii* and *Ralstonia pickettii*, causing diseases in a variety of plants while *Ralstonia pickettii* and *Ralstonia mannitolilytica*, act as opportunistic human pathogens, causing infections in immune-compromised individuals (Kim *et al.*, 2015).

Ralstonia solanacearum is highly diverse, exhibiting significant genetic and phenotypic variations, observed in its multiple races, biovars, and phylotypes (Wang *et al.*, 2023). Each variant revealed distinct characteristics, such as host range and virulence factors (Paudel *et al.*, 2020). Phylotypes are monophyletic clusters of strains (equivalent to subspecies or separate species) (Paudel *et al.*, 2020). The current classification of *R. solanacearum* is based on phylogenetic studies on the basis of whole genomes due to the inaccuracies of the earlier classifications (paudel *et al.*, 2020). Four phylotypes have been identified based on sequence analysis of the ITS (intergenic spacer) region in 2005 that later formed the basis for the separation of the *Ralstonia solanacearum* species complex (RSSC) into three distinct species in 2016. The phylotype-based classification system has persisted and recently in 2020 had been upgraded through recent technological advancements into phylogenetic studies of the whole genome (Paudel *et al.*, 2020). Studying the diversity of *R. solanacearum* in different regions allows for a comprehensive understanding of its genetic variation and evolution.

To sequence and identify bacterial wilt pathogens, commonly used genes include the 16S rRNA gene and the recA gene, which are highly conserved across bacterial species (Razia *et al.*, 2021; Yin *et al.*, 2022). Universal sequences such as the egl gene and the hrpB gene are specific to *R. solanacearum* and involved in pathogenicity (Mansfield *et al.*, 2012; Safni *et al.*, 2014). Additionally, the type III secretion system (T3SS) genes and the exopolysaccharide (EPS) biosynthesis gene cluster can serve as molecular markers for identifying and classifying *R. solanacearum* (Lowe-Power *et al.*, 2016; Bekeko *et al.*, 2020). These genes together with toxins (Lowe-Power *et al.*, 2016), and quorum sensing (Paudel *et al.*, 2020) help *R. solanacearum* to evade the defence mechanisms of the plant.

Different protocols have been employed for the extraction of *R. solanacearum* from infected tomato plants, including selective culture media, such as Sequeira semi-selective medium which have been instrumental in isolating and culturing *R. solanacearum* (Chen *et al.*, 2019; Su *et al.*, 2020). Furthermore, diverse methods, such

August 31, 2024

as commercial kits have been utilized to extract *R. solanacearum* DNA from tomatoes, culture media, soil samples, and water samples (Pendi & Hussain, 2020; Razia *et al.*, 2021). Nonetheless, easy contamination of growth medium by other microbes is common if proper equipment is not available for precise diagnosis of the *Ralstonia solanacearum*. Accurate and rapid detection of this pathogen is essential for disease management and prevention.

In this study, we bridged an information gap on the diversity of *R. solanacearum* in the region, facilitated by modified agar medium (MAM), Nutrient agar (NA) for isolation and Multiplex-Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) to elucidate the presence of four distinct phylotypes of *R. solanacearum* in Buea, Cameroon. These findings provide valuable insights for targeted control measures to mitigate the impact of the pathogen on tomatoes production and thereby increase and sustain the production of tomatoes in Cameroon.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study site

This study was carried out in Buea, Cameroon. Buea is situated in the Southwest Region of Cameroon, with geographical coordinates between latitude 3°57' to 4°27'N and longitude 8°58' to 9°25'E. It is positioned on the Eastern slope of Mount Cameroon, an active volcano. The region experiences a mean annual rainfall of approximately 2800 mm, primarily received from June to Early October (Egbe *et al.*, 2023). The average annual temperature is 28°C, mean relative humidity 86%, and sunshine duration ranges from 900 to 1200 hours per annum (Egbe *et al.*, 2023; Tambe *et al.*, 2024). Buea is characterised by its mountainous terrain, featuring dense evergreen forest vegetation at lower elevations and transitional changes along the altitudinal gradient. The predominant economic activity in this region is agriculture, primarily carried out through slash and burn and organized commercial plantations managed by the Cameroon Development Cooperation (CDC) (Tandi *et al.*, 2014)

The plant samples used for isolation and identification of *R. solanacearum* were collected from five tomato farming sites in Buea (Bwitingi, Ewonda, Great Soppo, Molyko, and Muea) located in Southwest region, Cameroon (Figure 1). The laboratory activities were carried out in the Clinical Diagnostic Laboratory and the Biotech Unit at the University of Buea.

August 31, 2024

Figure 1: Location of the Southwest Region of Cameroon (A), study sites in Buea located in Fako Division (B) and sites where samples were collected in Buea (C).

Sample Collection.

Samples were collected from three farms per site. For each farm, a systematic sampling approach was employed according to Umadevi *et al.* (2021). Three transects, each measuring 15m by 3m (45m²), were evenly laid out at regular intervals of 10m across the entire farm. The starting points of the collections were determined randomly to prevent any potential bias in the sampling process. Along each transect, a total of five quadrants, each measuring 1m by 3m (3m²), were randomly established. The placement of these quadrants ensured a comprehensive coverage of the study area. In each quadrant, plants were visually inspected for characteristic symptoms of tomato bacterial wilt disease (Nkoa *et al.*, 2015) and a quick diagnostic (stem streaming) test conducted in the field for all targeted plant specimens to be collected (Schacht *et al.*, 2011). To collect the samples, sterile blades were used to excise the plants approximately 10 cm above the soil line. This method ensured the collection of plant material that represented the affected portions and minimized the risk of contamination. Thirty plant samples were collected from each farm and divided into three batches of ten plant samples each to form a single sample. The disease symptoms that included wilting leaves, yellow leaves, decolourised xylem, and adventitious roots were recorded. To maintain the integrity and viability of the collected samples during transportation, samples were partitioned into equal sections and placed in labeled sterilised specimen containers (100 ml). The samples were stored inside these containers, which were then placed in ice packs. This was to ensure the samples remained in optimal condition, preserving their quality and minimizing any potential degradation or microbial growth during transit to the laboratory (Asif *et al.*, 2021).

The isolation and morphological characterisation of the *S. lycopersicum* bacterial wilt

At the laboratory, samples were surface-sterilized with 1% of 1M sodium hypochlorite for 10 minutes and rinsed in three changes of sterile distilled water to wash away any surface contaminants by other microorganisms (Ayana *et al.*, 2011). Sections of the stems were further cut into smaller pieces of 4 mm² (2 mm by 2mm) and plated on modified agar medium (MAM) that inhibited the growth of fungi and other bacteria (Ayana *et al.*, 2011) and later subcultured on nutrient agar. Plates were incubated at 28°C for 24 – 48 hours. *R. solanacearum* colonies were identified based on their typical morphology as described in Razia *et al.* (2021), sub-cultured on nutrient agar plates for purification by streaking (Pawaskar *et al.*, 2014; Sharma *et al.*, 2019). The isolates were then confirmed as *R. solanacearum* by performing pathogenicity test (Sharma, 2018) and biochemical tests (Kligler Iron Agar, KIA (Winans *et al.*, 2020) and Gram-staining (Omotayo & Eegunranti, 2023).

Preparation of modified agar medium (MAM)

Twenty eight grams of Nutrient agar (NA) (Oxoid, UK), was dissolved in 0.999 L of sterile distilled water supplemented with 5 ml glycerol to ensure sufficient nutrients for bacterial growth and the pH adjusted to 7.2. The nutrient agar was autoclaved at 121°C for 15 minutes under 2.02 x 10⁵ Pa. After autoclaving, the nutrient agar was cooled to 50-55°C, and Polymyxin B sulphate salt (100 mg/L), Chloramphenicol (5mg/L), Cycloheximide (100 mg/L), crystal violet (5mg/L), 2,3,5 triphenyl tetrazolium chloride (50 mg/L) were added to the nutrient agar (Sharma *et al.*, 2019). The nutrient agar was stirred gently until all the reagents were completely dissolved. Polymyxin B sulphate salt, and Chloramphenicol are broad-spectrum antibiotics that can inhibit the growth of a wide range of bacteria, including gram-negative bacteria like *Ralstonia solanacearum* (Wang *et al.*, 2014). Cycloheximide and penicillin besides being antibiotics are antifungal agents that can prevent fungal growth in the medium.

Preparation of nutrient agar

Following the manufacturer's instructions, 23.5 g of nutrient agar were weighed with an electronic balance and added to 1 L of distilled water in a 2L conical flask (Sharma, 2018). The mixture was thoroughly homogenized by continuous agitation, sealed with Aluminum foil, autoclaved at 121° C for 15 minutes at a pressure of 2.02 x 10⁵ Pa, and cooled to about 40 °C. 20 ml each of the prepared agar medium was poured into sterile labeled petri dishes in aseptic pouring techniques, swirled gently ensuring even distribution of the agar medium and avoidance of air bubble formation. The poured nutrient agar in the petri dishes was allowed to solidify.

August 31, 2024

Subculturing of Ralstonia solanacearum isolates on nutrient agar

Using a sterile inoculating loop, a loopful of each isolate obtained from the modified agar medium was streaked onto nutrient agar plates. These plates were incubated to facilitate regrowth of the isolates on the nutrient agar surface. To ensure ease of observation and interpretation of colony morphology, a 0.5 McFarland standard (1.5×10^8 CFU) was prepared. Serial dilutions ranging from 10^{-1} to 10^{-9} were subsequently prepared, and pour plates were used to subculture the diluted isolates until discrete and distinctive colony forming units (CFUs) were obtained, as outlined by Köhl *et al.* (2019).

A sterile pipette was employed to transfer 20 μ l of the serially diluted isolates to the centre of the nutrient agar plate (Pawaskar *et al.*, 2014; Sharma *et al.*, 2019). To ensure even distribution of the inoculum across the agar surface, the nutrient agar plates were gently tilted in various directions. This process was repeated for each nutrient agar plate. Once inoculated, the plates were allowed to air dry with the lids partially open to prevent condensation and these were done under aseptic conditions. In order to avoid any water droplets falling onto the agar surface, the plates were securely closed and inverted as recommended by Tu *et al.* (2020).

Biochemical test

Kliger Iron Agar (KIA) test

A total of 54.5 grams of Kliger iron agar were suspended in one liter of sterile distilled water, and the suspension was subjected to boiling while being continuously agitated to ensure complete homogenization of the solution. The resulting medium was then dispensed into screw-capped tubes, followed by autoclaving at a temperature of 121°C for a duration of 15 minutes. After autoclaving, the tubes were allowed to cool in a slanted position, resulting in the formation of short slopes and deep butts within the medium. In order to initiate inoculation, the centres of individual colonies were carefully selected using a sterile inoculating loop. The butt of the slant was inoculated by inserting the loop to the bottom, withdrawing it, and subsequently streaking the surface of the slant. To facilitate incubation, the caps of the tubes were slightly loosened, and the inoculated tubes were placed in an incubator set at a temperature of 36 °C for a period of 18-20 hours (Mazumder *et al.*, 2023). The uninoculated control involved preparing Kliger iron agar medium as described, without inoculation, and incubating under identical conditions (36°C for 18-20 hours).

Gram staining test

The isolates were adjusted to a 0.5 McFarland standard (1.5×10^8 CFU). One milliliter of the solution was smeared and heat-fixed onto a slide, which was then positioned on a staining rack above a sink. The slide was stained with crystal violet (8.16 mg/L) for one minute, followed by rinsing under tap water. 0.1% Gram's iodine was applied for one minute, and the slide was washed again. A decolouriser consisting of 95% alcohol was added for 10 seconds, and the slide was washed under tap water. Afterwards, a counterstain of 0.25% safranin was applied for one minute, followed by rinsing. The back side of the slide was cleared using tissue paper, and a drop of cedar wood oil was placed on the smear. The slide was then focused under a light microscope at 100X magnification and observed on a desktop screen (Omotayo & Eegunranti, 2023; Paray *et al.*, 2023).

Pathogenicity test

The virulence of the isolates was confirmed through pathogenicity testing. The soils were sterilized using steam at 100°C for 2 hours, as described by Conti *et al.* (2023). The poultry manure was disinfected by heating in an oven at 100 °C for 4 hours (Vazquez-Vazquez *et al.*, 2015). Tomato seedlings were raised on the sterilised soil in germination boxes with a soil-to-poultry-droppings ratio of 4:1. Following a three-week period, the seedlings were transplanted to labeled polythene bags containing nutrient-amended sterilised soil in three replicates per isolate. Sterilised needles were used to wound the lower stems and/or roots, and 5 ml of each bacterial isolate (1.5×10^8 CFU, McFarland Standard) were applied to the plant roots using a syringe. Control tests used distilled water. Tomato plants were observed for wilt symptoms (wilting, yellow leaves, stunted growth, xylem discoloration) for up to 14 days post-inoculation to determine pathogenicity as elucidated by Kumar & Doshi

(2018) and Mazumder *et al.* (2023). Disease symptoms were recorded, and symptomatic plants were re-isolated on nutrient agar plates.

Optimised protocol for DNA extraction of *R. solanacearum* using the quick-DNA Fungal/Bacterial Miniprep Kit

The protocol was based on the manufacturer's instructions (Zymo Research Corp). For optimal performance, beta-mercaptoethanol was added to the Genomic Lysis Buffer to a final dilution of 0.5 % (v/v) i.e., 500 µl per 100 ml. 50 – 100 mg (wet weight) of bacterial cells were resuspended in 200 µl of distilled water and transferred into a ZR BashingBead™ Lysis Tube (0.1 mm & 0.5 mm). 750 µl BashingBead™ Buffer was then added to the bacterial suspension. The ZR BashingBead™ Lysis Tube was secured in a bead beater fitted with a 2 ml tube holder assembly and vortexed for 10 minutes (GENIE). The ZR BashingBead™ Lysis Tube (0.1 & 0.5 mm) was centrifuged in a microcentrifuge (Thermo Scientific) at 10,000 x g for 1 minute. 400 µl of the supernatant was transferred to a Zymo-Spin™ III-F Filter in a collection tube and centrifuged at 8,000 x g for 1 minute. 1,200 µl of Genomic lysis buffer was added to the filtrate in the collection tube. 800 µl of the mixture from was transferred to a Zymo-Spin™ IICR column in a collection tube and centrifuged at 10,000 x g for 1 minute. The flow through was discarded from the collection tube and this step was repeated. 200 µl DNA pre-washed buffer was added to the Zymo-Spin™ IICR column in a new collection tube and centrifuged at 10,000 x g for 1 minute. 500 µl of g-DNA Wash Buffer was added to the Zymo-Spin™ IICR Column and centrifuged at 10,000 x g for 1 minute. The Zymo-Spin™ IICR column was transferred to a clean 1.5 ml microcentrifuge tube and 100 µl of DNA elution buffer added directly to the column matrix, centrifuged at 10,000 x g for 30 seconds to elute the DNA. Ultra-pure DNA was now ready for use in the experiments.

Optimization of a PCR protocol for the identification of *R. solanacearum*.

The extracted DNAs of the isolates of *R. solanacearum* collected from different locations were subjected to molecular detection by PCR. A pair of universal species-specific primer pair 759F (5'-GTC GCC GTC AAC TCA CTT TCC-3') and 760R (5'-GTC GCC GTC AGC AAT GCG GAA TCG-3') (Pendi & Hussain, 2020; Hossain *et al.*, 2021; Razia *et al.*, 2021) were used. PCR amplification was carried out in a total volume of 15 µl using 7.5 µl of PCR Master Mix (Thermo fisher), 1 µl of forward primer, 1 µl of reverse primer, 2 µl of genomic DNA and 3.5 µl of nuclease free water. The following cycling program was used in a thermal cycler (2720 Thermal Cycler, Applied Biosystem, Singapore): an initial denaturation step at 94°C for 5 mins, followed by 35 cycles of 94°C for 45 s, 62°C for 45 s and 72°C for 45 s, followed by a final extension step of 72°C for 3 mins. After completion of cycling program, reaction was held at 4°C. The PCR product of expected 280bp were separated on 2% Agarose gel stained with 0.5 uL (0.5 g/mL) of ethidium bromide for 15 mins at 120V and visualised using a Gel-Doc™ XR⁺ (BIO-RAD).

Optimization of a multiplex PCR protocol for the differentiation of *R. solanacearum* phylotypes.

Specific *R. solanacearum* phylotypes were identified using primers targeting the ipxC gene, which encodes for a protein unique to strains of all four phylotypes, as well as the ITS intergenic region between the 16S and 23S rRNA genes (Chen *et al.*, 2019; Razia *et al.*, 2021). The reverse primer Nmult22:RR is common to all four Phylotypes whereas the forward primers Nmult21:1F, Nmult21:2F, Nmult23:AF and Nmult22:InF are specific to Phylotypes I, II, III and IV, respectively. The thermocycler was programmed with the multiplex PCR conditions outlined above. The reaction components and volumes are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Multiplex PCR optimized reaction components

Reagent	Working conc.	Volume per reaction (uL)
Mastermix	N.A.	7.50
Molecular-grade water	N.A.	3.75
Forward primer (760)	100 uM	0.25
Reverse primer (759)	100 uM	0.25
Forward primer (Nmult21:1F)	100 uM	0.25
Forward primer (Nmult21:2F)	100 uM	0.25

August 31, 2024

Forward primer (Nmult23:AF)	100 uM	0.25
Forward primer (Nmult22:InF)	100 uM	0.25
Reverse primer (Nmult22:RR)	100 uM	0.25
Target DNA	N.A.	2
Total		15

Amplicon sizes in base pairs were as follows: 280 bp or 282 bp for primers 759/760. 144 bp for primers Nmult21:1F/Nmult22:RR, 372 bp for primers Nmult21:2F/Nmult22:RR. 91 bp for primers Nmult23:AF/Nmult22:RR. 213 bp for primers Nmult22:InF/Nmult22:R. The primer names, sequences and their specificity are indicated in Table 2

Table 2: The primer names, corresponding sequences, and their specificities

Primer name	Sequence	Specificity
759	5'-GTCGCCGTCAACTCACTTTCC-3'	All 4 Phylotypes
760	5'-GTCGCCGTGTCAGCAATGCGGAATCG-3'	All 4 Phylotypes
Nmult21:1F	5'-CGTTGATGAGGCGCGCAATTT-3'	Phylotype I
Nmult21:2F	5'-AAGTTATGGACGGTGGGAAGTC-3'	Phylotype II
Nmult23:AF	5'-ATTACGAGAGCAATCGAAAGATT-3'	Phylotype III
Nmult22:InF	5'-ATTGCCAAGACGAGAGAAGTA-3'	Phylotype IV
Nmult22:RR	5'-TCGCTTGACCCTATAACGAGTA-3'	All 4 Phylotypes

Source: Adapted from Hossain *et al.*, 2021; Razia *et al.*, 2021

Agarose gel electrophoresis of the PCR products

After running the multiplex PCR test for phylotype identification of *Ralstonia solanacearum*, the PCR products were subjected to agarose gel electrophoresis. 1g of agarose powder was weighed on an electronic balance, dissolved in 50 ml of Tris-acetate EDTA (Ethylenediaminetetraacetate) buffer and microwaved (Sharp, Grill Hot Air) for 2 minutes. The solution was then cooled and 0.5 µl of Ethidium bromide was added and the solution casted into a gel tray fitted with combs to create loading wells, avoiding air bubbles. The solution was allowed to solidify for 20 minutes. 10 µl of each PCR product was loaded in the wells alongside a 100 bp DNA ladder molecular marker (BenchTop, *New England Biolabs*). The gel was then run in a gel tank containing TAE buffer to provide electrolytes and ensure consistent electrophoretic conditions. The power pack was adjusted to 120 V, 700 mA, and 150 W, and electrophoresis was conducted for 15 minutes. The gel was then visualized in a gel-doc TM^{XR+} (BIO-RAD) using a Gel Imager Software and the resulting image displaced on a desktop screen.

Negative and positive controls were included in the PCR tests to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the results (Kumar *et al.*, 2016). In this study, four types of controls were included: a negative isolation control (NIC) using a universal fungi primer, a positive isolation control (PIC) with Bacterial universal primer, a negative amplification control (NAC) with molecular grade water, and a positive amplification control (PAC) with the species-specific primers. The NIC was used to monitor contamination during nucleic acid extraction, while the PIC was used to ensure that nucleic acid of sufficient quantity and quality was isolated. The NAC was included to rule out false positives due to contamination during the preparation of the reaction mix, while the PAC was used to monitor the efficiency of the amplification. Also, reaction components were agitated gently to avoid denaturation or shearing of the DNA.

Data analyses

The Kruskal-Wallis test and the Spearman correlation were used to examine the relationship between the number of wilted leaves, yellow leaves, discoloured xylems, and adventitious roots on the different samples collected.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The bacterial wilt symptoms recorded from the collected samples

The symptoms of bacterial wilt in tomato plants were observed in the five sites: Bwitingi, Great soppo, Ewonda, Molyko, and Muea. These symptoms included wilting, starting from the youngest leaves to the older ones, yellow leaves, stunted growth, brown discolouration of xylem, and the presence of numerous adventitious roots on the lower stems (Table 3).

Table 3: Bacterial wilt symptoms scored for affected plants for the samples collected.

Sites	Sample number	Number of wilted leaves	Number of yellow leaves	Discoloured xylem	Adventitious roots
Bwitingi	1	8	2	1	present
	2	4	1	1	absent
	3	7	0	1	absent
Great Soppo	1	11	0	1	present
	2	4	0	0	present
	3	5	0	2	present
Ewonda	1	32	3	1	present
	2	11	4	1	present
	3	12	6	1	absent
Molyko	1	23	0	0	absent
	2	4	8	0	present
	3	5	2	0	present
Muea	1	41	11	3	present
	2	15	4	3	absent
	3	13	0	3	present
H-Values	Df=2	4.76	1.29	0.52	
P-Values		0.092	0.52	0.771	

A sample was constituted by a batch of ten collected plants.

The results of the Kruskal-Wallis test indicated that there was no significant difference ($P = 0.05$) in the number of wilted and yellow leaves, discoloured xylems or adventitious roots among the samples (Table 3 and Figure 2). The Spearman correlation analysis revealed weak positive correlations coefficients between yellow leaves and wilted leaves ($r = 0.24$), and discoloured xylem and wilted leaves ($r = 0.43$). The correlation coefficient between discoloured xylem and yellow leaves was found to be weaker ($r = 0.13$) (Figure 2). These findings shed light on potential relationships among these symptoms in plant health. Further investigation is warranted to explore the underlying mechanisms. Similar symptoms have been reported by other authors including Kamalakannan *et al.* (2019) in Solanaceae crops; Razia *et al.* (2021) in potatoes; Sharma *et al.* (2019) and Silva *et al.* (2021) in tomatoes. These consistent symptoms across the sites suggest a widespread presence of bacterial wilt in the region, while the correlations indicated the complexity of disease progression.

August 31, 2024

Figure 2: Spearman correlation of wilted leaves, yellow leaves, and discoloured xylem. Where r is the correlation coefficient, CI is the confidence interval.

The isolation and morphological characterisation of the *S. lycopersicum* bacterial wilt

The symptomatic samples (Figure 3-A) showed a positive stem streaming test (Figure 3-B) and grew into colony forming units (CFUs) when cultivated on the modified agar medium (Figure 3-C) or nutrient agar plates (Figure 3-E). The virulent forms exhibited pearly cream-white, flat, irregular, and fluidal colonies with whorls in the centre, whereas avirulent forms displayed small, round, non-fluidal butyrous colonies that were entirely cream-white on nutrient agar (Figure 3-D). The KIA (Kligler Iron Agar) test for *R. solanacearum* isolates showed positive results for all five sites, with a characteristic yellow butt and slant indicating acid production from glucose fermentation (Figure 3-F). The control experiment, on the other hand, showed negative results, indicating that the observed acid production is specific to the *R. solanacearum* isolates. According to Winans *et al.* (2020), the Kligler Iron Agar test was positive for *R. solanacearum* due to the bacterium's ability to produce acid and gas from glucose fermentation. According to Omotayo & Eegunranti (2023), the Gram staining test was negative for *R. solanacearum* because the bacterium possesses a lipopolysaccharide layer in its cell wall, which prevented the retention of crystal violet stain during the staining process (Figure 3-E).

August 31, 2024

Figure 3: The symptoms of bacterial wilt (A & B: i-vii), isolation on MAM plates (C), sub-culturing on nutrient agar plates (D), Gram staining (E), and Kligler iron agar test (F).

Where i is a tomato plant showing stunted growth, ii depicts wilting leaves, iii are yellow leaves, iv shows discoloured xylem, v unveils exuding polysaccharides with *R. solanacearum* from affected plants, vi is showing adventitious roots and vii represents *R. solanacearum* seen under a light microscope.

The *R. solanacearum* colonies were identified based on their morphology (reddish and mucoid appearance) on the modified agar medium that was developed. The 2, 3, 5-Triphenyl tetrazolium chloride (TTC) as a redox indicator revealed the metabolic activity of bacteria by producing a brownish to reddish colouration used in the place of Tetrazolium chloride (TZC) (Sharma *et al.*, 2019; Sharma, 2018). Polymyxin B sulphate salt, and Chloramphenicol inhibited the growth of a wide range of bacteria, including gram-negative bacteria (Figure 3-E) (Pawaskar *et al.*, 2014; Sharma *et al.*, 2019) while Cycloheximide and penicillin prevented bacterial and fungal growth in the modified agar medium.

The pathogenicity tests

The *S. lycopersicum* (cobra tomatoes) in the pathogenicity test showed typical signs and symptoms of tomato bacterial wilt, including wilting starting with the youngest leaves followed by the older ones, yellow leaves, stunted growth, and brown discolourisation of xylem (Figure 4 and Table 4). These symptoms were consistent

August 31, 2024

with those observed in the field and further confirmed that the isolated pathogen, *R. solanacearum*, was responsible for the disease. Similar results in the pathogenicity test of *R. solanacearum* were observed by Asif *et al.* (2021) and Conti *et al.* (2023). These findings validated the ability of *R. solanacearum* to induce disease symptoms and establish its role as a pathogen in susceptible plant hosts, supporting previous research in the field (Kumar & Doshi, 2018; Sharma *et al.*, 2019; Mazumder *et al.*, 2023). This corroborates that the pathogen which was isolated was *R. solanacearum*.

Figure 4: Pathogenicity test results for *R. solanacearum* isolates from the samples. BW = Bacterial wilt.

August 31, 2024

Table 4: The responses of *R. solanacearum* isolates to the different tests.

Sites	Sample number	Stem streaming test	Growth on MAM	Growth on NA	Gram staining	Pathogenicity test	KIA test
Bitingi	1	3	3	3	3	1	2
	2	3	3	3	3	2	2
	3	2	3	3	3	3	3
Great Soppo	1	1	2	2	1	0	1
	2	1	3	3	2	0	1
	3	2	1	1	0	2	3
Ewonda	1	0	2	2	2	2	2
	2	0	2	2	1	1	2
	3	1	1	1	1	0	1
Molyko	1	1	3	3	2	2	2
	2	1	2	2	1	2	2
	3	2	3	3	0	2	2
Muea	1	3	2	2	0	1	3
	2	3	3	3	3	2	3
	3	3	3	3	3	0	3
	H- Value	11.82	6.86	6.86	6.61	4.75	6.92
	P-Value	0.019	0.143	0.143	0.158	0.314	0.140

In Table 4, the values 3, 2, 1, and 0 represent the number of replicates in the various samples numbered 1, 2 and 3 for all sites that showed positive results for the various tests conducted.

The results of the Kruskal-Wallis test on the various tests are shown on Table 4. The stem streaming test showed significant differences ($H = 11.82$, $p = 0.019$), suggesting variations across the sites. However, there were no significant differences at $P = 0.05$ found in growth of the different isolates on MAM ($H = 6.86$, $p = 0.143$), growth on NA ($H = 6.86$, $p = 0.143$), Gram staining ($H = 6.61$, $p = 0.158$), KIA ($H = 6.92$, $P = 0.140$), and Pathogenicity test ($H = 4.75$, $p = 0.314$). The significant site-specific differences in the stem streaming indicated variations in bacterial movement and morphology across the sites (Schacht *et al.*, 2011). However, there was no statistically significant differences observed in growth media, staining, KIA and pathogenicity tests contrasted with prior literature suggesting more stable and well adapted communities of the pathogen in Cameroon (Jiang *et al.*, 2013). This peculiar dichotomy suggests *Ralstonia solanacearum* maintains core physiological capabilities while diversifying in specialized traits such as movement, due to adaptations to local environmental conditions. Further investigation is necessary to elucidate the drivers associated with this key virulence-associated behaviour.

The molecular analyses of *R. solanacearum*

Genomic DNA extraction

Genomic DNA extraction yielded successful results for all the 45 isolates obtained from the three replicates of the 15 farms across the five sites. Figure 5A displays a band of the extracted genomic DNA. The presence of a clear band indicates that the DNA extraction process was highly effective, achieving a 100% success rate with all the samples involved.

August 31, 2024

Figure 5: The molecular analyses of *R. solanacearum* showing bands of extracted genomic DNA (A), amplified species specific DNA fragments (B), phylotype specific DNA fragments (C), and Fungal DNA fragment (D).

Where (A) 1% agarose gel: extracted genomic DNA, (B) 2% agarose gel: the PCR product of *R. solanacearum* (280 bp), (C) 2% agarose gel: differentiation of *R. solanacearum* phylotypes, (D) 2% agarose gel: Fungal amplification noticed before the MAM was produced. MW represents the Molecular Weight marker, NC stands for Negative Control, and the following site codes were used: GS for Great soppo, MU for Muea, BI for Bwitingi, EW for Ewonda, and MO for Molyko, These site codes indicate the specific sites from which the 45 isolates of *R. solanacearum* were obtained while the numbers 1 to 6 represented the replicates.

August 31, 2024

The high success rate achieved in this study aligns with the importance of reliable DNA extraction methods in genetic research (Konan *et al.*, 2020; Lee & Park, 2016). Efficient and accurate extraction of genomic DNA is crucial for subsequent analyses, such as PCR amplification, sequencing, and other genetic investigations. The successful extraction achieved in this study indicated that the chosen method was effective in obtaining high-quality genomic DNA from the *R. solanacearum* isolates.

Furthermore, the reliable DNA extraction provides a solid foundation for further analyses, such as genetic characterization (She *et al.*, 2017), identification of specific genetic markers (Kim *et al.*, 2021), or comparative genomics (Dahal *et al.*, 2010), evolutionary relationships (Mazumder *et al.*, 2023), and potential virulence factors (Lowe-Power *et al.*, 2018) of *R. solanacearum* isolates, contributing to a deeper understanding of the pathogen and aiding in the development of targeted control strategies (Mansfield *et al.*, 2012). This commendable outcome demonstrated the reliability and suitability of the DNA extraction method for future studies of a similar nature.

DNA amplification to ascertain the presence of *R. solanacearum* in the extracted DNA

Gel electrophoresis of the PCR products consistently yielded 280 bp DNA fragments for all 45 isolates (Figure 5B), using the species-specific primer pair 759F and 760R. These results differed from the findings of previous studies, such as Razia *et al.* (2021), who observed bands in only nine out of their fifty isolates, and Pendi & Hussain (2020), who encountered blurred bands using different DNA extraction buffers and methods. Therefore, these PCR amplification results not only confirm the presence of *R. solanacearum* in the isolates that cause tomato bacterial wilt disease but also suggest its widespread establishment in Buea and other regions of Cameroon. Importantly, the optimized protocol employed in this study holds promise for effective disease diagnosis.

Differentiation of *R. solanacearum* phylotypes using multiplex PCR

Table 5: The phylotype distribution of *R. solanacearum* by location.

Phylotypes	Base pairs (bp)	Codes	Bitingi	Great Soppo	Ewonda	Molyko	Muea
<i>R. solanacearum</i>	144	I	1	2	3	0	1
			3	1	3	0	2
			3	3	3	0	0
<i>R. pseudosolanacearum</i>	372	II	0	0	0	3	2
			0	0	0	2	0
			0	0	0	0	3
<i>R. syzygii</i>	91	III	0	3	0	0	3
			0	3	0	0	3
			0	3	3	3	3
<i>R. pickettii</i>	213	IV	0	0	2	3	3
			0	0	3	3	3
H- Values			10.38	7.08	10.41	7.54	11.00
P - Values			0.01	0.05	0.02	0.05	0.01

In Table 5, the values 3, 2, 1, and 0 represent the number of replicates in the sample that showed positive results. The multiplex PCR successfully amplified the various primers, revealing the different *R. solanacearum* phylotypes. The phylotypes of the extracted DNA (Figure 5C and Table 5) gave clear bands (372, 144, 213, and 91 bp) on a 1% agarose gel after electrophoresis (Figure 5B). These results unveiled the high diversity of *R. solanacearum* phylotypes present at the study sites. Phylotype I (*R. solanacearum*) and IV (*R. pickettii*), characterised by DNA fragments amplifying at 144 bp and 213 bp, respectively, were commonly observed, with Phylotype I isolated from Great Soppo, Muea, Ewonda, and Bwitingi, while Phylotype IV was detected in Great Soppo, Muea, Ewonda, and Molyko. Phylotype II (*R.pseudosolanacearum*) displaying DNA fragment

August 31, 2024

amplification at 372 bp and phylotype III (*R. syzygii*) with DNA fragment amplification at 91 bp were exclusively found in Muea and Great soppo.

These findings corroborated previous reports on the genetic diversity of *R. solanacearum* populations, which have shown the coexistence of multiple phylotypes in a given geographical region (Safni *et al.*, 2014). These results highlight the presence of phylotypes II and IV, which are non-indigenous to Africa, as noted in the review by Paudel *et al.* (2020). Additionally, the pathogen has become established in the soils, necessitating further studies to gain a clearer understanding and concerted efforts for its management. The site-specific differences in phylotype distribution highlight the importance of characterising the local *R. solanacearum* populations to inform the development of tailored management strategies. Further investigations into the ecological factors and genetic mechanisms underlying the observed phylotype variations could provide valuable insights for improved disease control.

The Fungi universal primer amplification was observed with isolates that were not subjected to treatment with Modified Agar Medium (MAM). Figure 5C clearly demonstrated that bands 3, 4, and 6, representing these isolates, exhibited amplification of a 490 bp DNA fragment. Conversely, isolates that were grown on MAM did not show amplification with the Fungi universal primer. This control step was essential to assess the presence of fungal DNA fragments and to ensure that the use of MAM and subculturing effectively eliminated any contamination of the samples by fungi.

Conclusion

The modified agar medium (MAM), optimized DNA extraction protocol, species-specific primers, multiplex PCR, and gel electrophoresis successfully identified and differentiated *R. solanacearum* phylotypes, ensuring accurate isolation and reliable results. The *R. solanacearum* phylotypes are highly diversified in Buea. Efficient methods for *R. solanacearum* identification in sub-Saharan Africa can improve detection, aiding in decisions making to control the disease and enhance food security. Further research on ecology, mitigation strategies, and taxonomy of the pathogen in the region would provide insights for prevention and environmentally friendly approach to combat the bacterial wilt affecting many food crops in Buea, Cameroon.

References

- i. Afanga, Y. A., Bechem, E. E., Egbe, E. A. (2022). Exploring tomato farmers perceptions with a view to produce local F1 hybrid in Buea, Cameroon. *International Journal of Agriculture and Biological Sciences.*, 1&2, 58–67.
- ii. Asif, S., Khan, M., Waqar Arshad, M., & Shabbir, M. I. (2021). PCR Optimization for Beginners: A Step by Step Guide. *Research in Molecular Medicine*, 9(2), 81–102. <https://doi.org/10.32598/rmm.9.2.1189.1>
- iii. Ayana, G. (2016). Bacterial wilt caused by *Ralstonia solanacearum* in Ethiopia: A Review. *International Journal of Phytopathology*, 05(03), 107–119.
- iv. Ayana, G., Fininsa, C., Ahmed, S., & Wydra, K. (2011). Effects of Soil Amendment on Bacterial Wilt Caused by *Ralstonia solanacearum* and Tomato Yields in Ethiopia. *Journal of Plant Protection Research*, 51(1). <https://doi.org/10.2478/v10045-011-0013-0>
- v. Ayankojo, I. T., Morgan, K. T., Kadyampakeni, D. M., & Liu, G. D. (2020). Tomato growth, yield, and root development, soil nitrogen and water distribution as affected by nitrogen and irrigation rates on a florida sandy soil. *HortScience*, 55(11), 1744–1755. <https://doi.org/10.21273/HORTSCI15177-20>
- vi. Bekeko, Z., Fininsa, C., Hussien, S., Hussien, T., & Wegari, D. (2020). Resistance of some selected maize genotypes to gray leaf spot disease (*Cercospora zae-maydis*) in Ethiopia. *Journal of Genes and Environmental Resources Conservation.*, 6(1), 1–13.
- vii. Chen, M. C., Wang, J. P., Zhu, Y. J., Liu, B., Yang, W. J., & Ruan, C. Q. (2019). Antibacterial activity against *Ralstonia solanacearum* of the lipopeptides secreted from the *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens* strain FJAT-2349. *Journal of Applied Microbiology*, 126(5), 1519–1529. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jam.14213>

August 31, 2024

- viii. Conti, V., Parrotta, L., Romi, M., Del Duca, S., & Cai, G. (2023). Tomato Biodiversity and Drought Tolerance: A Multilevel Review. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 24(12), 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms241210044>
- ix. Dahal, D., Pich, A., Braun, H. P., & Wydra, K. (2010). Analysis of cell wall proteins regulated in stem of susceptible and resistant tomato species after inoculation with *Ralstonia solanacearum*: A proteomic approach. *Plant Molecular Biology*, 73(6), 643–658. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11103-010-9646-z>
- x. Egbe, A. E., Solange, M., Soupi, N., Nkede, F., & Ndogho, A. P. (2023). Growth , yield and yield characteristics of three pepper cultivars to fertilizers application in the Mount Cameroon Region. *Journal of Agricultural Chemistry and Environment*, 12, 188–205. <https://doi.org/10.4236/jacen.2023.122015>
- xi. Elsayed, T. R., Jacquiod, S., Nour, E. H., Sørensen, S. J., & Smalla, K. (2020). Biocontrol of bacterial wilt disease through complex interaction between tomato plant, antagonists, the indigenous rhizosphere microbiota, and *Ralstonia solanacearum*. *Frontiers in Microbiology*, 10, 2835. <https://doi.org/http://10.3389/fmicb.2019.02835>
- xii. Gerszberg, A., & Hnatuszko-Konka, K. (2017). Tomato tolerance to abiotic stress: a review of most often engineered target sequences. *Plant Growth Regulation*, 83(2), 175–198. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10725-017-0251-x>
- xiii. Gupta, A., Kamalachandran, D., Longchar, B., & Senthil-Kumar, M. (2018). Impact of soil moisture regimes on wilt disease in tomatoes: Current understanding. *Biochemical, Physiological and Molecular Avenues for Combating Abiotic Stress in Plants*, 2005, 73–82. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-813066-7.00005-X>
- xiv. Hossain, M. F., Billah, M., Ali, M. R., Parvez, M. S. A., Zaoti, Z. F., Hasan, S. M. Z., Hasan, M. F., Dutta, A. K., Khalekuzzaman, M., Islam, M. A., & Sikdar, B. (2021). Molecular identification and biological control of *Ralstonia solanacearum* from wilt of papaya by natural compounds and *Bacillus subtilis*: An integrated experimental and computational study. *Saudi Journal of Biological Sciences*, 28(12), 6972–6986. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sjbs.2021.07.069>
- xv. Isidro-Requejo, L. M., Márquez-Ríos, E., Del Toro-Sánchez, C. L., Ruiz-Cruz, S., Valero-Garrido, D., & Suárez-Jiménez, G. M. (2023). Tomato plant extract (*Lycopersicon esculentum*) obtained from agroindustrial byproducts and its antifungal activity against *Fusarium spp.* *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 7, 1323489. <https://doi.org/http://10.3389/fsufs.2023.1323489>
- xvi. Jiang, J. F., Li, J. G., & Dong, Y. H. (2013). Effect of calcium nutrition on resistance of tomato against bacterial wilt induced by *Ralstonia solanacearum*. *European Journal of Plant Pathology*, 136(3), 547–555. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10658-013-0186-7>
- xvii. Kamalakannan, A., Krishnan, S., & Aundy, K. (2019). Characterization of *Ralstonia solanacearum* causing tomato bacterial wilt disease in Tamil Nadu and selection of potential antagonistic *Bacillus spp.* for its management. *Plant Disease Research*, 33(2), 191–201.
- xviii. Khatun, P., & Das, S. K. (2020). Medicinal and Versatile Uses of an Amazing, Obtainable and Valuable Grass: *Cynodon dactylon*. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medicinal Research Journal Homepage: Www.Ijpmr.Org Review Article*, 8(5), 1–11.
- xix. Kim, B. S., French, E., Caldwell, D., Harrington, E. J., & Iyer-Pascuzzi, A. S. (2015). Bacterial wilt disease: Host resistance and pathogen virulence mechanisms. *Physiological and Molecular Plant Pathology*, 95, 37–43. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pmpp.2016.02.007>
- xx. Kim, M., Nguyen, T. T. P., Ahn, J. H., Kim, G. J., & Sim, S. C. (2021). Genome-wide association study identifies QTL for eight fruit traits in cultivated tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.). *Horticulture Research*, 8(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41438-021-00638-4>
- xxi. Köhl, J., Kolnaar, R., & Ravensberg, W. J. (2019). Mode of action of microbial biological control agents against plant diseases: Relevance beyond efficacy. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 10(July), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2019.00845>

August 31, 2024

- xxii. Konan, N., Patrice Houphouet, Y., Konaté, I., Diallo Mamadou, S., Bakayoko, N., Ouattara, A., Sélastique Akaffou, D., & Mergeai, G. (2020). Breeding for resistance to tomato bacterial wilt: Identification of potential sources of genetic resistance by field evaluation of 28 tomato cultivars in Daloa, Côte d'Ivoire. *Journal of Agricultural and Crop Research*, 8(12), 305–313. https://doi.org/10.33495/jacr_v8i12.20.206
- xxiii. Kumar, J., & Doshi, A. (2018). Pathogenicity test and convenient inoculation method of *Xanthomonas axonopodis* pv. *vignaeradiatae* caused leaf spot of green gram. *International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences*, 7(04), 152–166. <https://doi.org/10.20546/ijcmas.2018.704.017>
- xxiv. Lee, J., & Park, T.-H. (2016). Isolation and characterization of bacteriophages infecting *Ralstonia solanacearum* from potato fields. *Research in Plant Disease*, 22(4), 236–242. <https://doi.org/10.5423/rpd.2016.22.4.236>
- xxv. Lee, P. Y., Costumbrado, J., Hsu, C. Y., & Kim, Y. H. (2012). Agarose gel electrophoresis for the separation of DNA fragments. *Journal of Visualized Experiments*, 62, 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.3791/3923>
- xxvi. Li, N., He, Q., Wang, J., Wang, B., Zhao, J., Huang, S., Yang, T., Tang, Y., Yang, S., Aisimutuola, P., Xu, R., Hu, J., Jia, C., Ma, K., Li, Z., Jiang, F., Gao, J., Lan, H., Zhou, Y., ... Yu, Q. (2023). Super-pangenome analyses highlight genomic diversity and structural variation across wild and cultivated tomato species. *Nature Genetics*, 55(5), 852–860. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41588-023-01340-y>
- xxvii. Lowe-Power, T. M., Jacobs, J. M., Ailloud, F., Fochs, B., Prior, P., & Allen, C. (2016). Degradation of the plant defense signal salicylic acid protects *Ralstonia solanacearum* from toxicity and enhances virulence on tobacco. *MBio*, 7(3), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1128/mBio.00656-16>
- xxviii. Lowe-Power, T. M., Khokhani, D., & Allen, C. (2018). How *Ralstonia solanacearum* Exploits and Thrives in the Flowing Plant Xylem Environment. *Trends in Microbiology*, 26(11), 929–942. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tim.2018.06.002>
- xxix. Mamphogoro, T. P., Babalola, O.O., and Aiyegoro, O. A. (2020). Sustainable management strategies for bacterial wilt of sweet peppers (*Capsicum annum*) and other Solanaceous crops. *Journal of Applied Microbiology*, 129, 496–508. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jam.14653>
- xxx. Mansfield, J., Genin, S., Magori, S., Citovsky, V., Sriariyanum, M., Ronald, P., Dow, M., Verdier, V., Beer, S. V., Machado, M. A., Toth, I., Salmond, G., & Foster, G. D. (2012). Top 10 plant pathogenic bacteria in molecular plant pathology. *Molecular Plant Pathology*, 13(6), 614–629. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1364-3703.2012.00804.x>
- xxxi. Martinez, S., Gabriel, J. L., Allende-Montalbán, R., San-Juan-heras, R., & Delgado, M. D. M. (2022). The Application of a Bio-Stabilized municipal solid waste-based fertilizer for buckwheat production. *Agriculture (Switzerland)*, 12(6), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture12060776>
- xxxii. Mayele, J. M., & Abu, F. R. (2023). Determining the effects of selected organic fertilizer on growth and yields of tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum*: Var. Rio Grande Tomatoes) in Mundri West County, Western Equatoria State, South Sudan. *Agricultural Sciences*, 14(09), 1343–1374. <https://doi.org/10.4236/as.2023.149089>
- xxxiii. Mazumder, R., Hussain, A., Rahman, M. M., Phelan, J. E., Campino, S., Abdullah, A., Clark, T. G., & Mondal, D. (2023). Genomic and functional portrait of multidrug-resistant, hydrogen sulfide (H₂S)-producing variants of *Escherichia coli*. *Frontiers in Microbiology*, 14(July), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2023.1206757>
- xxxiv. Nkoa, R., Owen, M. D. K., & Swanton, C. J. (2015). Weed abundance, distribution, diversity, and community analyses. *Weed Science*, 63(Special issue), 64–90. <https://doi.org/10.1614/ws-d-13-00075.1>
- xxxv. Omotayo, O. E., & Eegunranti, A. M. (2023). Effect of soil solarization on tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) growth and impact on native microbial diversity of farm soil in Nigeria. *Egyptian Journal of Biological Pest Control*, 33(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41938-023-00653-8>
- xxxvi. Osipitan, O. A., Yahaya, I., & Adigun, J. A. (2018). Economics of weed management methods as influenced by row-spacing in Cowpea. *Journal of Agricultural Science*, 10(2), 98.

<https://doi.org/10.5539/jas.v10n2p98>

- xxvii. Paray, A. A., Singh, M., & Amin Mir, M. (2023). Gram staining: A brief review. *International Journal of Research and Review*, 10(9), 336–341. <https://doi.org/10.52403/ijrr.20230934>
- xxviii. Paudel, S., Dobhal, S., Alvarez, A. M., & Arif, M. (2020). Taxonomy and phylogenetic research on *Ralstonia solanacearum* species Complex: A complex pathogen with extraordinary economic consequences. *Pathogens*, 9(886), 1–26.
- xxxix. Pawaskar, J., Joshi, M. S., Navathe, S., Agale, R. C., & Sawant Konkan Krishi Vidyapeeth, B. (2014). Physiological and biochemical characters of *Ralstonia solanacearum*. *International Journal of Research in Agricultural Sciences*, 1(6), 2348–3997.
- xl. Pendi, F. H., & Hussain, H. (2020). Suitability of various buffers for genomic DNA extraction of pineapple (*Ananas comosus*) var. MD2. *Journal of Sustainability Science and Management*, 15(8), 90–101. <https://doi.org/10.46754/JSSM.2020.12.008>
- xli. Petropoulos, S. A., Fernandes, Â., Xyrafis, E., & Polyzos, N. (2020). The optimization of nitrogen fertilization regulates crop performance and quality of processing Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L. cv. Heinz 3402). *Agronomy*, 10(715), 19.
- xlii. Planas-Marquès, M., Kressin, J. P., Kashyap, A., Panthee, D. R., Louws, F. J., Coll, N. S., & Valls, M. (2020). Four bottlenecks restrict colonization and invasion by the pathogen *Ralstonia solanacearum* in resistant tomato. *Journal of Experimental Botany*, 71(6), 2157–2171. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jxb/erz562>
- xliii. Razia, S., Chowdhury, M. S. M., Aminuzzaman, F. M., Sultana, N., & Islam, M. (2021). Morphological, pathological, biochemical and molecular characterization of *Ralstonia solanacearum* isolates in Bangladesh. *American Journal of Molecular Biology*, 11(04), 142–164. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ajmb.2021.114012>
- xliv. Safni, I., Cleenwerck, I., Vos, P. De, Fegan, M., Sly, L., & Kappler, U. (2014). Polyphasic taxonomic revision of the *Ralstonia solanacearum* species complex: proposal to emend the descriptions of *Ralstonia solanacearum* and *Ralstonia syzygii* and reclassify current *R. syzygii* strains as *Ralstonia syzygii* subsp. *syzygii* subsp. *nov.*. *International Journal of Systematic and Evolutionary Microbiology*, 64, 3087–3103. <https://doi.org/10.1099/ijs.0.066712-0>
- xlv. Schacht, T., Unger, C., Pich, A., & Wydra, K. (2011). Endo- and exopolygalacturonases of *Ralstonia solanacearum* are inhibited by polygalacturonase-inhibiting protein (PGIP) activity in tomato stem extracts. *Plant Physiology and Biochemistry*, 49(4), 377–387. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.plaphy.2011.02.001>
- xlvi. Sharma, D. K. (2018). Morphological and biochemical characterization of *Ralstonia solanacearum* (smith) in brinjal (*Solanum melongena* L.) in Rajasthan (India). *Advances in Plants & Agriculture Research*, 8(3), 284–288. <https://doi.org/10.15406/apar.2018.08.00328>
- xlvii. Sharma, D., & Singh, Y. (2019). Characterization of *Ralstonia solanacearum* isolates using biochemical, cultural, molecular methods and pathogenicity tests. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*, 8(4), 2884–2889. <https://www.phytojournal.com/archives/2019/vol8issue4/PartAU/8-4-392-512.pdf>
- xlviii. She, X., Yu, L., Lan, G., Tang, Y., & He, Z. (2017). Identification and genetic characterization of *Ralstonia solanacearum* species complex isolates from *Cucurbita maxima* in China. In *Frontiers in Plant Science* (Vol. 8). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2017.01794>
- xlix. Shibzukhov, Z. G., Bagov, A., Shibzukhova, Z., Khantsev, M., & Akbar, I. (2021). Tomato productivity depending on mineral nutrition and irrigation regimes in the conditions of film greenhouses in the mountain zone of the KBR. *E3S Web of Conferences*, 262. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202126201032>
- l. Silva, C. J., Van Den Abeele, C., Ortega-Salazar, I., Papin, V., Adaskaveg, J. A., Wang, D., Casteel, C. L., Seymour, G. B., & Blanco-Ulate, B. (2021). Host susceptibility factors render ripe tomato fruit vulnerable to fungal disease despite active immune responses. *Journal of Experimental Botany*, 72(7),

- 2696–2709. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jxb/eraa601>
- li. Su, L., Zhang, L., Nie, D., Kuramae, E. E., Shen, B., & Shen, Q. (2020). Bacterial tomato pathogen *Ralstonia solanacearum* invasion modulates rhizosphere compounds and facilitates the cascade effect of fungal pathogen *Fusarium solani*. *Microorganisms*, 8(6), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms8060806>
- lii. Tambe, A. A., Mfombep, P. M., Julie, D. T., Egbe, L. E., Tabot, P. T., Dengiz, O., & Agbor, D. T. (2024). Tomato varieties superiority assessment under organic and inorganic (granular and foliar) fertilization in sandy clay soil. *Eurasian Journal of Soil Science inorganic (granular and foliar) fertilization in sandy clay soil*. 13(1), 1–9.
- liii. Tessema, L., Seid, E., Woldegiorgis, G., & Sharma, K. (2020). Current status of bacterial wilt (*Ralstonia solanacearum*) disease in major seed potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.) growing areas of Ethiopia. *Journal of Plant Pathology & Microbiology*, 11(5), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.35248/2157-7471.20.11.497>
- liv. Toukam, G. M. S., Gilles, C., Wicker, E., Guilbaud, C., Kahane, R., Allen, C., & Prior, P. (2009). Broad diversity of *Ralstonia solanacearum* strains in cameroon. *Plant Disease*, 93(11), 1123–1130. <https://doi.org/10.1094/PDIS-93-11-1123>
- lv. Tripodi, P., D'Alessandro, A., & Francese, G. (2023). An integrated genomic and biochemical approach to investigate the potentiality of heirloom tomatoes: Breeding resources for food quality and sustainable agriculture. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 13(January). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2022.1031776>
- lvi. Umadevi, U., Narasimha Murthy, K., Gayathri Devi, N., & Srinivas, C. (2021). Isolation and identification of bacterial wilt causing *Ralstonia solanacearum* from groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea* L.). *International Journal of Agricultural Technology*, 17(2), 767–780.
- lvii. Umesha, S., & Avinash, P. (2015). Multiplex PCR for simultaneous identification of *Ralstonia solanacearum* and *Xanthomonas perforans*. *3 Biotech*, 5(3), 245–252. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13205-014-0223-z>
- lviii. Vazquez-Vazquez, C., Gallegos-Robles, M. A., Salazar-Sosa, E., Orona-Castillo, I., Garcia-Hernandez, J. L., Trejo-Escareño, H. I., & Mendoza-Retana, S. S. (2015). Manure solarization from cattle, goat and poultry and its effect on survival of *Salmonella spp*. *Journal of Pure and Applied Microbiology*, 9(1), 151–158.
- lix. Wang, Z., Luo, W., Cheng, S., Zhang, H., Zong, J., & Zhang, Z. (2023). *Ralstonia solanacearum* – A soil borne hidden enemy of plants: Research development in management strategies, their action mechanism and challenges. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 14(February), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2023.1141902>
- lx. Winans, K., Brodt, S., & Kendall, A. (2020). Life cycle assessment of California processing tomato: An evaluation of the effects of evolving practices and technologies over a 10-year (2005–2015) timeframe. *International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*, 25(3), 538–547. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-019-01688-6>
- lxi. Włodarczyk, K., Smolińska, B., & Majak, I. (2023). The antioxidant potential of Tomato plants (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) under nano-ZnO treatment. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 24(14), 11833. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms241411833>
- lxii. Yin, J., Zhang, Z., Guo, Y., Chen, Y., Xu, Y., Chen, W., Shao, Y., Yu, Y., Zhu, L., Chen, L., & Ruan, L. (2022). Precision probiotics in agroecosystems: multiple strategies of native soil microbiotas for conquering the competitor *Ralstonia solanacearum*. *MSystems*, 7(3). <https://doi.org/10.1128/msystems.01159-21>
- lxiii. Yusuf, Y. M., Madukwe, D. K., & Kebede, F. (2023). Establishing phosphorus critical values for tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*) fertilization with phosphate fertilizers on the Sudan savanna soils using three soil phosphorus extraction methods and field experimentation in Kano State, Nigeria. *Frontiers in Agronomy*, 5(August), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fagro.2023.1181045>